

Affordability-led decisions impacting households' health and economic wellbeing - A transdisciplinary perspective

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Background. Housing affordability is often measured by the rent-to-income ratio, which risks houses being deemed affordable despite poor quality (AHC, 2019). Low-income families often have no choice but to live in these homes, exacerbating health inequality issues. Issues can arise from excessive cold and mold in winter (Boomsma et al., 2017) or overcrowdedness, affecting mental health and educational outcomes and spreading respiratory infectious diseases (WHO, 2018). During COVID-19, residents of poor quality housing recorded high death rates (OECD, 2020). Poor quality houses affect residents' Health and Economic Wellbeing (H+EW) and strain national health systems, leading to illnesses and accidents that cost the National Health Service £1.4 billion per year (Garrett et al., 2021). Despite ongoing efforts to improve the housing stock, the burden of poor quality housing still exists (EHS, 2020). A key factor determining housing quality is the decisions made during the design stages (Mulliner et al., 2013; RIBA, 2020). Therefore, to mitigate future risks of new affordable homes turning into the poor quality and harming residents' H+EW, there is a need for a transdisciplinary understanding of the affordability-led decisions that guide design stages.

Aim. As part of a PhD project, the study aims to answer the question of what affordability-led decisions impact design stages and households' H+EW.

Method. The study adopts a transdisciplinary approach to allow a deeper insight beyond disciplines' biases to understand what decisions may influence affordable houses design that later impact its residents' H+EW. Thus, six semi-structured interviews were conducted with professionals from social housing associations, and architecture practice and academia who participated in the design stages of affordable housing in England. In this study, "Affordability-led decisions" refers to the decisions taken to make a house affordable to build or affordable to live in. The "affordable houses" refer to England's housing schemes that support low to moderate-income households, whether from private, local, or social housing providers. Finally, "design stages" refer to the first five stages of the RIBA plan of work (RIBA, 2020), where decisions on the design, construction, and materials selection are made.

Results. Three patterns of affordability-led decisions at design stages impact future residents' H+EW were captured from the interviews, as follows:

1. The first pattern is early design stages decisions to reduce initial investment costs by densifying units, building on distant locations, or sacrificing higher sustainability standards. An architect described affordable housing as: "It is often in the worst place, and it has to be built as densely as possible while adopting minimum standards, which creates long-term wellbeing problems" (A1). Another referred to developers requesting densification by "fitting as many units as possible on one plot" and "compromising between quality and quantity of units" (A2), due to the continuous rise in construction prices. Densification also means minimizing indoor and outdoor spaces by "squeezing down areas and sacrificing balconies" (A2), which often leads to an uneven distribution of daylight and good views among units. Finally, sacrificing higher sustainability standards and meeting the minimum requirements of national building regulations, is another form of reducing initial costs. For instance, it might be decided: "not to install renewables or use heat pumps instead of gas boilers".

2. The neglect of future Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ), encompassing thermal, visual, and acoustical comfort, as well as indoor air quality, constitutes a second pattern identified in the participants' narratives. For instance, hiring an IEQ expert to assess design decisions, material choices, and system selection is uncommon, due to saving pre-construction costs during technical design stages. Instead, decision-making often relies on national building regulations, design briefs, and architects' experience. This approach risks making inappropriate decisions, such as using an inadequate ventilation system or prioritizing insulation over ventilation, resulting in mold and dampness issues. These issues can be mitigated by utilizing small, consistently working mechanical ventilation systems. However, participants from housing associations prefer natural ventilation to save on recurring maintenance cost and operational expenses charged to residents who may be hesitant to use energy-consuming ventilation systems.
3. The third pattern prioritizes long-term thinking across all design stages to provide energy-efficient homes, reducing future energy bills. Passivhaus standard was indicated as the energy-efficient solution to making homes more affordable and healthier for occupants. While the adoption of Passivhaus standard may entail higher initial costs, it reduces energy bills and recurring maintenance associated with mold and dampness due to good airtightness and ventilation. However, this adoption is still a challenge. One participant from a housing association highlighted that: "We want to build Passivhaus homes, but it takes time to build a supply chain that is capable of building Passivhaus homes" (H1). Therefore, certain housing providers use the more practical Association for Environment Conscious Building standard, which aligns with Passivhaus principles. However, some participants cautioned that investing that investing in expensive insulation and windows without ensuring proper installation for airtightness can result in low energy efficiency and consequently become a waste of money.

Conclusions. The study identified three patterns of affordability-led decisions during the design stages that influence H+EW, from interviews, as illustrated in Figure 1. The first pattern prioritizes reducing initial costs through densification and sacrificing higher sustainability standards. The second pattern neglects aspects of IEQ. Both patterns pose health risks such as overcrowding, excessive cold, overheating, and mould. The third pattern is a long-term approach to providing energy-efficient homes. These patterns come from the real-world experiences of architects and housing providers and offer important insights into the challenges of delivering affordable and healthy homes in England. The study adds to the existing literature on the need to look at housing affordability beyond "rent to income" ratios. It highlights how health inequalities can originate from decision-making in the design stages. Further research is therefore needed to explore cost-effective and mutually beneficial design solutions between affordable housing providers and households H+EW.

Keywords. Health, Affordability, Economic wellbeing, Housing, Design, and Decision-making.

Figure 1

Chart by the author illustrating the relationships between the three patterns, impacts on design stages decisions, and impacts on residents' H+EW as identified by research participants and in reference to the WHO housing and health guidelines (WHO, 2018).

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